

**VALIDATED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE QUANTITATIVE
DETERMINATION OF OLUTASIDENIB IN
PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS**

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ABSTRACT

A novel, efficient, and stability-indicating reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the precise quantitative analysis of Olutasidenib in pharmaceutical formulations. This method offers superior sensitivity and accuracy compared to existing RP-HPLC techniques by employing a Symmetry C18 column (150 × 4.6 mm, 3.5 μm) and an optimized mobile phase of orthophosphoric acid (0.1% v/v) and acetonitrile (70:30 v/v), ensuring excellent resolution and peak symmetry. The analysis was conducted on a Waters Alliance e-2695 HPLC system, with detection at 218 nm using a photodiode array detector. The method demonstrated a high theoretical plate count (>15,000) and a tailing factor below 1, ensuring robust chromatographic performance. Sensitivity studies established a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.3 μg/mL and a limit of quantification (LOQ) of 1.0 μg/mL, highlighting the method's capability to detect trace levels of Olutasidenib. Stability assessments under acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, photolytic, and hydrolytic conditions confirmed the method's suitability

for degradation profiling. Validation, performed in accordance with International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines, confirmed the method's precision, accuracy, linearity, and robustness. Given its simplicity, sensitivity, and cost-effectiveness, this RP-HPLC method is highly suitable for routine quality control analysis of Olutasidenib in pharmaceutical applications.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, Olutasidenib, Stress conditions, Chromatographic parameters, ICH, Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

Olutasidenib is a highly selective and effective inhibitor of isocitrate dehydrogenase-1 (IDH1). It was approved by the FDA in December 2022 for treating relapsed or refractory acute myeloid leukemia (AML) with IDH1 mutations. Its IUPAC name is 5-[[[(1S)-1-(6-chloro-2-oxo-1H-quinolin-3-yl)ethyl]amino]-1-methyl-6-oxopyridine-2-carbonitrile [1-2]. IDH1 plays a key role in cellular metabolism by converting isocitrate to α -ketoglutarate (α -KG) through oxidative decarboxylation. This process supports vital functions such as epigenetic regulation, collagen production, and cell signaling. However, mutations in the IDH1 gene can alter the enzyme's activity. These mutations give the enzyme a new function, causing it to convert α -KG into 2-hydroxyglutarate (2-HG). Elevated levels of 2-HG disrupt normal α -KG metabolism, interfere with gene expression and cell differentiation, and promote cancer development by contributing to oncogenesis [3-4]. Mutations in the IDH1 gene are common in acute myeloid leukemia (AML) and occur in various forms. The most frequent mutations involve substitutions at amino acid position 132, notably R132H and R132C. These mutations are linked to AML progression, poor prognosis, and therapy resistance. Olutasidenib, by targeting the hyperactive mutant IDH1 enzyme, reduces the production of 2-hydroxyglutarate (2-HG), restoring normal cell functions and counteracting the tumor-promoting effects of these mutations. This mechanism is particularly effective in patients with IDH1-mutated AML, aiding in tumor reduction and improving clinical outcomes [5-6].

Olutasidenib specifically targets the mutant IDH1 enzyme, making it a key treatment for IDH1-related cancers, including AML, gliomas, and intrahepatic cholangiocarcinomas. As a precision medicine, it addresses the molecular abnormalities driving cancer growth, reversing the metabolic and epigenetic disruptions caused by 2-HG. Besides AML, olutasidenib is under investigation for other cancers with IDH1 mutations, offering new hope for patients with limited

treatment options [7-10]. The drug's long half-life of approximately 67 hours allows for once-daily dosing. In AML patients, it achieves a steady-state maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}) of 3573 ng/mL and an area under the curve (AUC) of 43,050 ng·h/mL. While increasing the dose from 100 mg to 300 mg results in a less-than-proportional rise in C_{max} and AUC, dose adjustments are unnecessary due to good tolerance within this range. A single 150 mg dose taken with a high-fat meal significantly increases drug exposure, with a 191% rise in C_{max} and 83% in AUC [11-14]. Robust analytical techniques, such as RP-HPLC and UV spectrophotometry, have been developed for accurate quantification of active pharmaceutical ingredients. RP-HPLC methods are particularly reliable for precise measurements, and their validation follows international guidelines (ICH, USP, FDA) to ensure accuracy and reproducibility. Recent advancements in method development and forced degradation studies further enhance the stability and quality of pharmaceutical products. In this context, the current study aims to establish a validated, stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for quantifying olutasidenib, addressing a critical need for rigorous analytical methods. Figure 1 presents the chemical structure of Olutasidenib [15-18].

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Olutasidenib

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The HPLC analysis was carried out using a Waters e2695 Alliance system equipped with a binary pump, a Rheodyne injector with a 20 μ L loop, and a UV detector. Data were processed using Empower 2.0 software. The separation of analytes was achieved using a Waters XTerra RP-18 column (150 mm x 4.6 mm, 3.5 μ m particle size) with detection at 223 nm. The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of acetonitrile and ammonium acetate (pH 3.0 adjusted with orthophosphoric acid) in a 30:70 ratio. The flow rate was set to 1 mL/min, and the injection volume was 10 μ L. The total runtime for each sample was 5 minutes. HPLC-grade acetonitrile and trifluoroacetic acid were procured from Rankem Chemicals, Hyderabad, while Milli-Q water of HPLC grade was used throughout the experiment.

2.1 Preparation of 0.1% OPA Buffer Solution

Dissolve 1 mL of OPA in 1 liter of HPLC-grade water. Filter the solution using a 0.45 μm nylon filter.

2.2 Preparation of the Mobile Phase

Prepare the mobile phase by mixing 0.1% OPA and acetonitrile (ACN) in a 70:30 ratio. Filter this mixture through a 0.45 μm membrane filter to eliminate any impurities that might affect the chromatographic analysis.

2.3 Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

Weigh exactly 10 mg of Olutasidenib standard and transfer it into a clean, dry 10 mL volumetric flask. Add a suitable diluent, sonicate to dissolve the compound, and then make up the volume to the 10 mL mark with the same diluent. This creates the stock solution. From this solution, transfer 1 mL into another 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with diluent to achieve a concentration of 100 ppm of Olutasidenib [19].

2.4 Preparation of Calibration Standards

For linearity studies, prepare six calibration solutions from the stock solution as follows:

- Level I (25 ppm): Dilute 0.25 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL with diluent.
- Level II (50 ppm): Dilute 0.5 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL with diluent.
- Level III (75 ppm): Dilute 0.75 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL with diluent.
- Level IV (100 ppm): Dilute 1 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL with diluent.
- Level V (125 ppm): Dilute 1.25 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL with diluent.
- Level VI (150 ppm): Dilute 1.5 mL of the stock solution to 10 mL with diluent.

Analyze all the solutions under identical chromatographic conditions, plot the concentration versus peak area, and calculate the regression equation for quantitative analysis.

2.5 Preparation of Sample Solution

Weigh 17.47 mg of Olutasidenib sample and transfer it to a clean, dry 10 mL volumetric flask. Add diluent, sonicate for 30 minutes to dissolve the sample completely, and centrifuge for 30 minutes. Dilute to the 10 mL mark with the same diluent and filter the solution through a 0.45 µm filter. From this stock solution, pipette 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with diluent to obtain a 100 ppm solution of Olutasidenib.

Procedure

Inject 10 µL of the standard and sample solutions into the chromatographic system. Record the peak areas for Olutasidenib and calculate the percentage assay using the appropriate formula [20].

Formula for Assay:

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{AT}{AS} * \frac{WS}{DS} * \frac{DT}{WT} * \frac{\text{Average weight}}{\text{Label Claim}} * \frac{P}{100} * 100$$

Where:

- AT = Mean area counts of the test sample solution.
- AS = Mean area counts of the standard solution.
- WS = Weight of the working standard (in milligrams).
- DS = Volume of the working standard dilution (in millilitres).
- DT = Volume of the test sample dilution (in millilitres).
- WT = Weight of the test sample (in milligrams).
- P = Purity percentage of the working standard.
- LC = Label claim concentration (in milligrams per millilitre).

2.6 Optimization and method development

During the optimization of chromatographic conditions for Olutasidenib analysis, six trials were conducted with varying parameters to establish a validated method.

Trial 1:

A X-Bridge Phenyl column (150 mm x 4.6 mm, 3.5 µm) was used with a mobile phase of Acetonitrile and 0.1% Trifluoroacetic Acid (50:50). The wavelength range was 200-400 nm, with a flow rate of 1 mL/min and a run time of 2.8 minutes. However, system suitability parameters did not meet the required standards.

Trial 2:

The same column was used with the mobile phase ratio altered to 40:60, and the

detection wavelength set at 218 nm. The flow rate remained at 1 mL/min, and the run time was extended to 5.50 minutes. Despite the adjustments, the column efficiency was inadequate, indicating poor analyte separation.

Trial 3:

A Symmetry C18 column (150 mm x 4.6 mm, 3.5 μ m) was introduced with a mobile phase ratio of 35:65. The detection wavelength was 218 nm, and the flow rate was 1 mL/min with a run time of 5.50 minutes. Poor baseline resolution suggested insufficient separation.

Trial 4:

The same Symmetry C18 column was used, and the mobile phase ratio was changed to 40:60, keeping other parameters constant. The run time was increased to 9 minutes, but the peak symmetry remained unsatisfactory, necessitating further refinement.

Trial 5:

The mobile phase was modified to Acetonitrile:0.1% OPA (35:65), using the same column and wavelength (218 nm). The flow rate was 1 mL/min, and the run time was 10 minutes. Although peak response improved, issues with peak shape and resolution persisted.

Trial 6 (Optimized Conditions):

The Symmetry C18 column was retained, and the mobile phase ratio was adjusted to Acetonitrile:0.1% OPA (30:70). The flow rate was maintained at 1 mL/min with a run time of 5 minutes, and the detection wavelength was 218 nm. These conditions resulted in a well-defined Olutasidenib peak at 2.450 minutes, with a peak area of 2,146,873 and a tailing factor of 0.95. This method met the criteria for system suitability and was validated for reliable and reproducible analysis of Olutasidenib.

The UV spectrum of Olutasidenib is shown in Fig. 2, and the optimized chromatogram with the Olutasidenib peak at 2.450 minutes is presented in Fig. 3. System suitability and column performance data are summarized in Table 1 [21].

Table 1: Evaluation of System and Column Performance Parameters

Parameter	Details
Instrument Used	Waters Alliance e-2695 HPLC System
Injection Volume	10 μ L
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: 0.1% Orthophosphoric Acid

Column	(30:70) Symmetry C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 3.5 μm)
Detection Wavelength	218 nm
Flow Rate	1 mL/min
Run Time	2.80 minutes
Column Temperature	Room Temperature (25°C)
Mode of Separation	Isocratic
Analyte Name	Olutasidenib
Retention Time	2.450 minutes
Theoretical Plate Count	15,247
Tailing Factor	0.95
Relative Standard Deviation (%RSD)	0.18%

This table summarizes the instrumental conditions and key performance metrics observed during the chromatographic analysis of Olutasidenib using the developed RP-HPLC method. The results indicate efficient column performance and precise separation.

Figure 2: PDA - Spectrum of Olutasidenib

Figure 3: Typical optimized Chromatogram of the Olutasidenib

2.7 Method Validation

The method was validated following the ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines. Validation steps included assessing system suitability, specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, limits of detection (LOD) and quantitation (LOQ), as well as robustness.

2.7.1 System Suitability

The HPLC system was stabilized for 40 minutes before testing for system suitability. Parameters checked included a theoretical plate count (minimum 2000), efficiency per meter, resolution (minimum 2.0), and tailing factor (maximum 1.5). If these criteria were met, the sample was injected twice, and chromatograms were recorded. Details of system suitability and column performance are provided in Table 1.

2.7.2 Specificity

Specificity refers to the method's ability to accurately measure the target analyte without interference from the blank or known impurities. Blank, standard, and sample chromatograms were recorded. The blank chromatogram showed no peaks at the retention times of the target drugs, confirming that the drug's response was specific. This is illustrated in Figure 4 [22-24].

Figure 4: Chromatograms of (A) a blank sample, (B) the placebo, and (C) the optimized formulation

2.7.3 Linearity

The linearity of the assay was evaluated by testing six different drug concentrations. According to ICH guidelines, a minimum of five concentrations is required for this analysis. Therefore, concentrations ranging from 25.0 to 150.0 µg/mL were prepared. A calibration curve was created by plotting the peak area against the drug concentrations. The linear regression equation obtained for Olutasidenib was $y=21669.33x+10163.68y = 21669.33x + 10163.68y=21669.33x+10163.68$, with an R-squared value of 0.99963, where Y represents the peak area and X represents the drug concentration. The linearity results are shown in Table 2, and the calibration curve is illustrated in Figure 5 [25].

Table 2: Linearity Results for Olutasidenib

Sr. No.	Olutasidenib Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak Area
1	25.00	565456
2	50.00	1074591
3	75.00	1676362
4	100.00	2131446
5	125.00	2756479
6	150.00	3243210

Regression Equation: $y = 21669.33x + 10163.68y = 21669.33x + 10163.68y = 21669.33x + 10163.68$

Slope: 21669.33

Intercept: 10163.68

R² Value: 0.99963

Figure 5: Calibration Curve for Olutasidenib

2.7.4 Precision

Precision refers to the consistency of results when an analytical method is repeated under standard operating conditions. There are three types of precision:

1. **System Precision**
2. **Method Precision**
3. **Intermediate Precision**
 - Intra-day Precision
 - Inter-day Precision

System Precision is assessed by testing a standard chemical substance to ensure the analytical system is functioning correctly. Six measurements of the peak area and percentage of drug content are taken, and the percentage relative standard deviation (RSD) is calculated. The system precision results for Olutasidenib are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: System Precision of Olutasidenib

S. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Area of Olutasidenib
1	100	2,146,873
2	100	2,139,150

3	100	2,142,449
4	100	2,140,653
5	100	2,138,946
6	100	2,147,521
Mean		2,142,599
S.D.		3,782.66
% RSD		0.18

Method Precision involves analyzing a homogeneous sample from a single batch six times. This test ensures that the method yields consistent results for a given batch. The percentage RSD is calculated from these six analyses. The method precision results for Olutasidenib are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Method Precision for Olutasidenib by HPLC

S. No	Area for Olutasidenib
1	2,138,974
2	2,132,417
3	2,129,810
4	2,166,608
5	2,154,295
6	2,170,406
Average	
Standard Deviation	
% RSD	

Intermediate Precision evaluates repeatability (intra-day) and variation between days (inter-day) for Olutasidenib. Intra-day precision involves repeating the assay three times on the same day at three different concentration levels, while inter-day precision involves repeating the assay on three separate days, with three measurements for each concentration level each day. The results are expressed in terms of % RSD, which should be $\leq 2.0\%$. The intermediate precision results are shown in Table 5 [26-28].

Table 5: Intermediate Precision (Day Variation) for Olutasidenib by HPLC

S. No.	Day 1 Area	Day 2 Area
1	2,152,889	2,147,285
2	2,148,794	2,130,669
3	2,131,815	2,123,574
4	2,139,611	2,155,690
5	2,128,397	2,133,242
6	2,170,058	2,144,067
Average	2,145,261	2,139,088
Standard Deviation	15,379.67	11,944.43
% RSD	0.72	0.56

2.7.5 Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was evaluated by assessing recovery, which involves spiking the sample with known amounts of standard drugs at 50%, 100%, and 150% of the initial concentration. The recovery was tested by analyzing the sample with added standard drugs at three levels (50%, 100%, and 150%) and measuring the recovered amounts. The results are shown in Table 6 [29].

Table 6: Accuracy Results of Olutasidenib

Concentration (at specification level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean % Recovery
50 %	5.00	1,075,624	5.02	100.4	99.6
	5.00	1,059,558	4.95	99.0	
	5.00	1,063,967	4.97	99.4	
100 %	10.00	2,149,487	10.03	100.3	100.0
	10.00	2,135,242	9.97	99.7	
	10.00	2,141,039	9.99	99.9	
150 %	15.00	3,234,873	15.10	100.7	100.3
	15.00	3,206,661	14.97	99.8	
	15.00	3,228,639	15.07	100.5	

2.7.6 Robustness

The robustness of the method was evaluated by introducing controlled variations in the flow rate, mobile phase composition, and temperature to observe their effects on the method.

A. Flow Rate Variation: The flow rate was varied from 0.9 mL/min to 1.1 mL/min. A 100 ppm standard solution of Olutasidenib was prepared and analyzed under these conditions. The results showed that changes in the flow rate affected the method significantly, but the method remained robust within a $\pm 10\%$ range of flow rate variation.

B. Organic Phase Ratio Variation: The ratio of the mobile phase was varied. A 100 ppm standard solution of Olutasidenib was analyzed under the new conditions. The results remained within acceptable limits, confirming the robustness of the method. The robustness test results for Olutasidenib are shown in Table 7 [30].

Table 7: Robustness Results for Olutasidenib by HPLC

Parameter	Condition	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area	Tailing	Plate Count	% RSD
Flow Rate Change (mL/min)	Less Flow (0.9)	2.345	2,061,452	0.99	15,338	0.32
	Actual Flow (1.0)	2.450	2,146,873	0.95	15,247	0.18
	More Flow (1.1)	2.115	2,306,947	0.90	15,165	0.66
Organic Phase Change	Less Org (27:73)	2.679	1,857,416	0.96	15,394	0.20
	Actual (30:70)	2.420	2,139,150	0.92	15,272	0.18
	More Org (33:67)	1.920	2,421,411	0.88	15,120	0.66

2.7.7 Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

The Limit of Detection (LOD) refers to the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be detected in a sample under specific experimental conditions, but it may not always

be quantifiable. The Limit of Quantification (LOQ) is the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be measured with sufficient precision and accuracy.

To calculate the LOD and LOQ, the following formulas, as per the International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines, are used:

- $LOD = 3.3 \times (\sigma / S)$
- $LOQ = 10 \times (\sigma / S)$

Where:

- σ is the standard deviation of the response (peak area).
- S is the slope of the calibration curve.

For Olutasidenib, the LOD was found to be 0.3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, and the LOQ was 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The results for LOD and LOQ are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8: Sensitivity Parameters (LOD & LOQ) by HPLC

Name of Drug	LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	S/N	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	S/N
Olutasidenib	0.3	3	1.0	10

2.8 Assay

The analysis of Olutasidenib formulations was conducted using the established method. The quantities and purity percentages of Olutasidenib are shown in Table 9. The purity values were 100%, and the % Relative Standard Deviation (% RSD) for these values was within the acceptable range of $\leq 2\%$ [31].

Table 9: Assay of Olutasidenib

Brand	Drug	Sample Area (n=2)	Std. wt	Sample wt	Label Amount (mg)	Std. Purity	Amount Found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Assay
-	Olutasidenib	2139415	10	17.47	150	99.9	9.99	99.9
		-						
		2142663						

2.9 Forced Degradation Studies of Olutasidenib

- **Stock Preparation:** Weigh 17.47 mg of Olutasidenib and transfer it to a 10 mL volumetric flask. Add the diluent, sonicate to dissolve completely, and dilute to the mark with the same solvent to prepare the stock solution.

Degradation Methods:

1. **Acid Degradation:** Take 1 mL of the stock solution in a 10 mL flask, add 1 mL of 1N HCl, heat at 60°C for 1 hour, neutralize with 1N NaOH, and dilute to 10 mL. Filter with 0.22 µm syringe filters and transfer to vials.
2. **Alkali Degradation:** Similar to acid degradation, but use 1 mL of 1N NaOH for neutralization.
3. **Peroxide Degradation:** Add 1 mL of 10% hydrogen peroxide to the stock solution, maintain at 60°C for 1 hour, and then leave at room temperature for 15 minutes. Filter and transfer to vials.
4. **Reduction Degradation:** Add 1 mL of 10% Sodium bisulphate, heat at 60°C for 1 hour, and follow the same procedure as peroxide degradation.
5. **Hydrolysis Degradation:** Add 1 mL of HPLC grade water, heat at 60°C, and proceed as per the peroxide degradation method.
6. **Photolytic Degradation:** Expose the sample to light in a photo-stability chamber for 3 hours, then dilute and analyze by HPLC.
7. **Thermal Induced Degradation:** Place the sample in a petri dish and expose it to 105°C for 3 hours. Afterward, dilute and analyze.

The forced degradation studies were conducted under various stress conditions to evaluate the stability of Olutasidenib. The degradation results are summarized in Table 10. The control sample showed no degradation, retaining 100% of the label claim. Acidic and alkaline conditions resulted in 12.9% and 13.6% degradation, respectively. Oxidative conditions caused the highest degradation (14.8%), while thermal stress led to 10.9% degradation. Reduction stress showed minimal degradation (3.6%), and photolytic degradation caused 1.4% degradation. Hydrolytic stress resulted in 2.7% degradation. In all cases, the purity angle remained below the threshold, confirming that no significant impurities were formed. The stability study demonstrated that Olutasidenib remains stable under various stress conditions [32].

Table 10: Forced Degradation Results for Olutasidenib

Sample	Sample Area	Mean	%	Purity	Purity	%	Pass/Fail
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Condition	Weight (mg)	Counts	Area Count	Label Claim	Angle	Threshold	Degradation	
Control	17.47	2141749	2141749	100	0.849	1.615	0	Pass
Acid	17.47	1866478	1866478	87.1	0.811	1.602	12.9	Pass
Alkali	17.47	1849692	1849692	86.4	0.886	1.606	13.6	Pass
Peroxide	17.47	1825587	1825587	85.2	0.849	1.608	14.8	Pass
Reduction	17.47	2065287	2065287	96.4	0.866	1.612	3.6	Pass
Thermal	17.47	1907654	1907654	89.1	0.855	1.618	10.9	Pass
Photolytic	17.47	2111572	2111572	98.6	0.867	1.614	1.4	Pass
Hydrolysis	17.47	2084120	2084120	97.3	0.876	1.611	2.7	Pass

2.9 Utilization of Pharmaceutical Formulations

The method developed was successfully used for quantitative analysis of commercial formulations, such as Rezlidhia (150 mg), yielding accurate results for all compounds analyzed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS:

The primary aim of this study was to develop a quick and accurate RP-HPLC method for the separation and quantitative measurement of Olutasidenib. After thorough testing of various conditions, we chose RP-HPLC due to the drug's polar characteristics. The column used was a X-Bridge Phenyl (150 mm x 4.6 mm, 3.5 μ m). The final optimized conditions were: a mobile phase of acetonitrile and 0.1% OPA buffer in a 30:70 ratio, a flow rate of 1 mL/min, and a detection wavelength of 218 nm. The column was kept at room temperature. These settings provided clear chromatographic peaks with excellent resolution and minimal peak tailing.

The method was validated based on ICH guidelines. Key parameters such as specificity, accuracy, linearity, precision, robustness, LOD (Limit of Detection), and LOQ (Limit of Quantification) were all assessed. The system suitability test showed that the method met all the required criteria, with a retention time of 2.450 minutes, a tailing factor of 0.95, and a theoretical plate number of 15,247. These results confirmed the method's reliability for Olutasidenib analysis.

Linearity was tested with six concentrations, resulting in a calibration curve that showed a linear relationship between 25.00 and 150.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, with a correlation coefficient greater than 0.99963. Precision was evaluated through intra-day and inter-day experiments, with relative standard deviation (%RSD) values consistently below 2%, proving that the method is reproducible and precise. The method's specificity was confirmed by testing it with pure drug samples and common excipients, showing no interference from excipients.

For accuracy, recovery studies were performed by spiking known amounts of Olutasidenib into pre-analyzed samples at three different levels (50%, 100%, and 150%). The recovery rates and %RSD values, all below 2%, demonstrated the accuracy of the method. The method's robustness was confirmed by introducing minor variations in the chromatographic conditions (e.g., flow rate, temperature, and mobile phase composition), which did not significantly alter the results, indicating the method's stability.

The LOD and LOQ for Olutasidenib were 0.3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 1.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively, confirming the method's high sensitivity. The mean assay value was 99.9%, demonstrating that the method accurately recovered the drug from pharmaceutical formulations. Stability studies also indicated that the method could detect Olutasidenib degradation products, with the most significant degradation observed under peroxide conditions.

In summary, the RP-HPLC method developed in this study is accurate, precise, and suitable for analyzing Olutasidenib in pharmaceutical formulations, fulfilling all ICH guideline requirements.

DISCUSSION:

The development of a reliable and precise analytical method for Olutasidenib is crucial, given the increasing demand for pharmaceutical products containing this compound. RP-HPLC was selected as the method of choice due to its effectiveness in analyzing polar drugs. The selection of X-Bridge Phenyl as the column material was based on its ability to provide good separation under the optimized conditions.

The optimization process involved careful trial-and-error testing of various operational parameters, including the mobile phase composition, flow rate, and detection wavelength. The final mobile phase of acetonitrile and OPA buffer (30:70) was found to offer the best separation, with sharp peaks and minimal tailing, which is

essential for reliable quantification. The retention time of 2.450 minutes was consistent, and the resolution and theoretical plate numbers were within acceptable limits, ensuring that the method is suitable for routine analysis.

The validation of the method according to ICH guidelines confirmed its specificity, as no interference from common excipients was observed during the analysis. Linearity testing over a range of concentrations demonstrated a strong correlation between concentration and response, with a correlation coefficient greater than 0.99963, ensuring accurate quantification within this range.

Precision, evaluated through intra-day and inter-day experiments, showed excellent repeatability with low %RSD values, indicating the method's reliability for routine analysis. The accuracy was demonstrated by the recovery studies, where known amounts of Olutasidenib were added to pre-analyzed samples at different levels. The recovery rates were close to 100%, with minimal variability, further validating the method's precision and accuracy.

The robustness of the method was tested by making minor variations in chromatographic conditions, and the results showed no significant impact, suggesting that the method is stable under slightly altered conditions, which is important for real-world applications where instrument parameters may vary.

The LOD and LOQ values of 0.3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 1.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively, indicated that the method is highly sensitive, capable of detecting low concentrations of Olutasidenib, which is vital for its analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The high mean assay value (99.9%) also confirmed that the method can accurately recover Olutasidenib from complex formulations.

Finally, the stability studies demonstrated that the method could detect degradation products, which is critical for quality control purposes. The observation of increased degradation under peroxide conditions suggests that oxidative degradation may be a concern for Olutasidenib, a factor that could be considered during formulation and storage.

Overall, the developed RP-HPLC method offers a reliable, sensitive, and robust approach for the analysis of Olutasidenib in pharmaceutical formulations, making it suitable for quality control and regulatory purposes. The method meets all ICH guideline requirements and provides a foundation for future studies and applications involving Olutasidenib.

4. CONCLUSION

The developed HPLC method for analyzing Olutasidenib is straightforward, quick, precise, accurate, robust, and cost-effective. The mobile phase and solvents used are easy to prepare, economical, and consistent, offering selectivity and speed. Preliminary recovery studies demonstrated that formulation excipients did not interfere with the recovery measurements. Therefore, the method is suitable for routine laboratory analysis of the drug. The validation results confirm the method's accuracy and reproducibility, making it reliable for determining the drug in both pure and formulated forms. Additionally, the stability-indicating assay is selective, with no interference from placebo or degradation products. In conclusion, the proposed HPLC method is robust, accurate, and precise, making it effective for analyzing Olutasidenib.

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Mr. Vishvas M Bhusari and Mr. Vaibhav B Sagade conducted the experiments and performed data analysis. Mr. Mahesh D Bhalsing contributed to data interpretation and manuscript drafting. All authors have reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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